

TECHNIQUES TO IMPROVE ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS

Isamidinova Gulchexraxon Komiljonovna

Andijon mashinasozlik instituti akademik

litseyi ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi.

Abstract. In this article, opinions were expressed about the methods of formation of speaking skills.

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There are also a variety of techniques to help improve your English speaking skills. Try your hand (or should we say mouth) at these:

Speech shadowing: Basically, this is copying how a native speaks. Speech shadowing can be done most simply by watching videos or a movie with subtitles. First, read the sentence and speak it out loud. Then, play it back with the native speaker speaking it. Try to pause in between to copy the flow and pattern as closely as possible. If you want, you can record yourself doing this to compare it with the way the native speaker sounds.

Self-talk: Whether you choose to speak your thoughts out loud or record yourself singing, talking to yourself and hearing the words will help you improve. You can also read out loud.

Think in English: This probably won't come naturally, but you can help train yourself to think in English by first translating the thoughts in your head. Otherwise, you can keep a journal or diary of thoughts and write them in English.

Retell a story in English: Start with something simple, like a fairytale or traditional story from your childhood. Then you can take this to the next step and challenge yourself to retell a story that someone else shares in English. This helps to check your comprehension and understanding.

Frequently Practice to Improve Your English Speaking Skills

From friends to strangers, you can always find someone who speaks English to practice with. Here are a few more ideas on how and where you can speak English:

Participate in public speaking events: Public speaking events, from forums and conferences to slam poetry events, offer a good place to listen to others speak. You can also potentially apply to be a speaker. If it's something less formal, like sharing your creative writing or telling a story in front of a small group of friends, public speaking can really showcase your skills.

Go to language cafes: Language cafes exist around the world. This is a place for people to come together and practice the languages of their choice in small group settings.

Using apps: Technology is here to assist in learning languages. From apps like Duolingo to Busuu, which lets you speak to native speakers, you can improve your English speaking skills wherever you go.

Chat with Siri: Want to speak to someone at a random time of night or simply set reminders on your phone to benefit your productivity? Chat with Siri!

Strategies and English Trainings

Everyone has their own favorite methods and ways of improving their English communication. There is no one right or wrong choice, so you can pick as many or as few as you wish and mix it up:

Talk to Yourself: Share your thoughts or read out loud.

Use a Mirror: Watch yourself speak to build confidence.

Focus on Fluency, Not Grammar: It's ok to take time to learn grammar. But it's more important to be able to communicate your thoughts first.

English Tongue Twisters: Try English tongue twisters to master the sounds of each letter.

Listen and Repeat: Practice and keep practicing by listening and repeating what you hear.

Pay Attention to Stressed Sounds: The language has a rhythm and certain syllables are stressed in both words and sentences.

Sing Along to English Songs: Use music to memorize words.

Learn Phrases, Not Words: By learning longer phrases, you combine words in context and can memorize both their meaning and pronunciation.

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